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LINGUOPRAGMATICS AS THE BRANCH OF MODERN LINGUISTICS

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***Abstract.** This article focuses on the study of linguopragmatics, one of the branches of contemporary linguistics, and its emergence as an independent field of study. It theoretically outlines that linguopragmatics was originally part of semiotics, later separated from it, and evolved into one of the new directions in modern linguistics. Additionally, a passage from A. Kadiri's novel was analyzed through the lens of "politeness," a significant topic in linguopragmatics.*

***Keywords.** Pragmatics, semantics, syntax, semiotics, communicative intention, speaker, listener*

Introduction. Linguistics has evolved as a science that studies language, its characteristics, and development stages. Initially recognized as an independent discipline, researchers later acknowledged the importance of the human factor in understanding language phenomena. This led to the realization that examining

language without considering human influences is inadequate. Significant attention is now given to how people conceptualize the world through language, as well as their speech and reactions to events. Additionally, non-linguistic factors such as age, origin, gender, religion, profession, and culture have become important. Consequently, fields like text linguistics, cultural linguistics, psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, and cognitive linguistics have emerged in modern linguistic studies.

Main part. Initially, the American scientist Charles Morris studied the field of pragmatics, incorporating it into the study of linguistic signs, known as semiotics. Along with Charles Peirce, Morris divided semiotics into three distinct parts: semantics, syntax, and pragmatics. The scientist S. Levinson clarifies this classification as follows: “Within semiotics, Morris distinguished three branches of inquiry: syntactics (or syntax), which is the study of the formal relations of signs to one another; semantics, the study of the relations of signs to the objects they represent (their designata); and pragmatics, the study of the relationship of signs to their interpreters.” It is important to note that syntax examines the syntactic relationships between signs, semantics focuses on the relationship of signs to the objects they can represent, and pragmatics looks at the relationship of signs to their users. To elaborate on these ideas, the scientist Sh. Safarov explains in his monograph: “For pragmatics, the questions of why (for what purpose) a person uses a sign and how (in what manner) this is done are important. This includes the use of involuntary signs, combined with inquiries about the formation of linguistic structures (syntax) and whether these structures of symbols can express the meanings desired by users (semantics).” Therefore, pragmatics cannot be completely separated from syntax and semantics; instead, it is a field that studies these areas in harmony with one another.

While semantics and syntax focus on the meanings of signs and the relationships between words, they do not address the attitudes of the speaker and

listener toward the words and speech. Pragmatics specifically examines why a user selects a particular word or symbol for a given purpose. Since the 1970s, various scholars have conducted scientific research in the field of linguo-pragmatics. Several definitions of linguo-pragmatics exist, along with the problems it address. J. Mey defines linguo-pragmatics as follows: “Linguo-pragmatics is a branch of linguistics and semiotics that studies the circumstances and ways in which context influences meaning. Pragmatics encompasses theories of speech acts, the processes of communication, interaction in conversation, and other features related to language within a speech situation.”

In addition to its connections with linguistics and semiotics, this field also intersects with philosophy, sociology, and anthropology. Consequently, we can assert that pragmatics is an interdisciplinary science.

Research methodology: Scholars around the world have proposed various theoretical definitions of pragmatics. Summarizing these definitions, we can present them in the following sequence:

- Ch. Morris (1938) defines pragmatics as the study of the relationship between a sign and its users.

- G. Gazdar (1979) posits that pragmatics can be expressed as Meaning minus Truth conditions.

- S. Davis (1991) states that pragmatics explains the communicative intentions and behaviors of the speaker, as well as the strategies used to ensure these intentions are understood by the listener.

- S. Liu (2001) describes pragmatics as the communicative actions of individuals in specific speech situations, highlighting a focus on how language is understood and produced.

- G. Moore (2001) defines pragmatics as a systematic approach to explaining language use in context.

- S. Levinson (2008) considers pragmatics to be the study of the relationship between language and context, which is embedded in grammatical structure and examines their dependence on each other. Additionally, Z. Moshood provided a dictionary definition of pragmatics: "The New Webster Dictionary of the English Language (1993) defines pragmatics as the science of the relationship between symbols, their interpretations, and users." This definition emphasizes the speaker's true intentions and distinguishes between the formal meanings of words and their context-based meanings in discourse.

Conclusion. Each natural language reflects a certain way of conceptualizing (perceiving and organizing) the world. Being the constitutive thinking ability of a person, language reflects the experience of human interaction with the environment and it is this, objectified in language in its entirety, which forms the linguistic picture of the world. Thus, linguopragmatics is a branch of linguistics that studies linguistic phenomena from the point of view of their use in specific communicative situations. The basic concepts of linguistic pragmatics play an important role in the analysis and understanding of people's linguistic behavior, their application helps to improve communication skills, resolve conflicts, and successfully interact with other people in the modern world, where communication plays a key role in all spheres of life. Unlike other areas of linguistics focused on the structure of language, linguopragmatics explores the use of linguistic means to achieve certain goals in communication, as well as differences in the use of language in different cultures and contexts.

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**ENGLISH IDIOMS AND PROVERBS THAT INVOLVES THE NAMES OF ANIMALS
AND THEIR EQUIVALENTS IN UZBEK LANGUAGE**

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***Abstract.** The terms and idioms that are commonly used in Uzbek talks are included in this page along with their English equivalents. By emphasizing their meanings and usage, it also provides excellent illustrations. Furthermore, certain popular Uzbek and English idioms are pointed out and adequately explained in this page. Idioms are proverbs that are based on common occurrences that illustrate human behavior, societal characteristics, or particular customs or traditions in a nation. They are a reflection of the sum total of human experiences. They are a legacy of the collected experiences that constitute a nation's or humanity's collective consciousness, and they almost serve as life lessons. Every nation or country has its own idioms that are unique to its culture, and many of these idioms have counterparts in other nations that speak to the same human character. You can learn more about a culture's history, customs, social structures, and material characteristics by becoming familiar with its distinctive idioms. Reading can help you learn more idioms. Many books, novels, and articles quote*